

TRAINING YOUNG RESEARCHERS ON SHAPING METAVERSE
FOR BUSINESS AND SOCIAL VALUE

DC14 – PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

Research Study: Complementor Influence on Digital Responsibility in Metaverse Platform Business Models

Principal Investigator: Milena Di Nenno

Affiliation: Cyprus University of Technology

Ethics Approval: Bioethics Committee of Cyprus University of Technology

1. Research Purpose

You are invited to participate in a research study investigating how complementors (third-party creators and developers) influence digital responsibility within metaverse platform ecosystems. This research examines your experiences, perspectives, and influence on platform business models, particularly regarding responsible business practices.

2. What Participation Involves

Participation involves a semi-structured interview lasting approximately 60-90 minutes, conducted via video conferencing. You will be asked about your experiences as a complementor, how you interact with and influence the platform, and your views on digital responsibility within the platform ecosystem. The interview will be audio/video recorded (with your permission) and transcribed for analysis.

3. Voluntary Participation and Right to Withdraw

Your participation is entirely voluntary. You may decline to answer any question and may withdraw from the study at any time without consequences. If you withdraw, all data collected from you will be permanently deleted upon request.

4. Confidentiality and Anonymization

Your identity will be protected through the following measures:

- Your real name will be replaced with a pseudonym in all transcripts, reports, and publications
- Any identifying information (specific projects, distinctive roles, company names) will be removed or disguised
- If you hold a prominent role that might make you identifiable despite anonymisation, explicit permission will be sought before including any potentially identifying information
- Data will be stored securely in encrypted formats with access restricted to the research team

Given the power dynamics between platforms and complementors, particular care will be taken to ensure you can safely discuss platform governance issues without risk of identification.

5. Data Usage and Storage

Interview data will be used for the PhD research project and may be included in academic publications, conference presentations, and the doctoral thesis. Anonymous excerpts from your interview may be quoted in these outputs. Data will be retained in accordance with institutional guidelines and securely destroyed after the required retention period.

6. Risks and Benefits

There are minimal risks associated with participation. You may experience minor discomfort discussing platform governance or conflicts. Benefits include contributing to an understanding of metaverse ecosystems and potentially influencing how metaverse platforms engage with their partners regarding responsibility issues.

7. Contact Information

If you have questions about the research, please contact Milena Di Nenno at md.dinenno@edu.cut.ac.cy

Consent Statement

I confirm that:

- I have read and understood the information about this research study
- I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the study
- I understand that my participation is voluntary and I may withdraw at any time
- I understand how my data will be used and protected
- I consent to the interview being audio/video recorded
- I agree to participate in this research study

Participant Name: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Researcher Name: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____